

INFLUENCE OF SAQ TRAINING ON SPEED AND AGILITY AMONG COLLEGE MEN STUDENTS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was designed to examine the effect of SAQ training on speed and agility of college men students. For the purpose of the study, thirty men students from the University College of Arts, Tumkur University, Tumkur, Karnataka, India were selected as subjects. They were divided into two equal groups. Each group consisted of the fifteen subjects. Group I underwent SAQ training for three days per week for twelve weeks. Group II acted as control who did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical education programme. The following variables, namely speed and agility were selected as criterion variables. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected dependent variables by using 50 mts run and shuttle run respectively at prior to and immediately after the training programme. The analysis of covariance was used to analyze the significant difference if any among the groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the 'F' ratio obtained by the analysis of covariance, which was considered appropriate. The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between SAQ training group and control group on speed and agility. And also it was found that there was a significant improvement on speed and agility due to twelve weeks of SAQ training.

Key Words: SAQ Training, Speed, Agility, College Men Students

Introduction:

SAQ training, which stands for Speed, Agility, and Quickness training, is a specialized form of exercise aimed at improving an individual's ability to move efficiently and effectively in various directions and at varying speeds. It's a cornerstone in the training regimens of athletes across a spectrum of sports, from soccer and basketball to martial arts and tennis. The primary goal of SAQ training is to enhance an athlete's performance by developing their speed, agility, and quickness attributes. Speed refers to how fast an individual can move over a specific distance, agility involves the ability to change direction rapidly, and quickness pertains to the speed at which an athlete can react to a stimulus.

SAQ training typically includes a combination of drills, exercises, and movements designed to target specific muscle groups and movement patterns. These might include ladder drills, cone drills, plyometric exercises, and directional changes. By consistently engaging in SAQ training, athletes can improve their acceleration, deceleration, change of direction, coordination, and overall athletic performance. In addition to athletes, SAQ training can benefit individuals seeking to improve their fitness levels, as it offers a dynamic and engaging way to enhance cardiovascular endurance, strength, and overall agility. Whether you're a competitive athlete or someone looking to elevate their fitness game, SAQ training can be a valuable addition to your workout routine.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was designed to examine the effect of SAQ training on speed and agility of college men students. For the purpose of the study, thirty men students from the University College of Arts, Tumkur University, Tumkur, Karnataka, India were selected as subjects. They were divided into two equal groups. Each group consisted of the fifteen subjects. Group I underwent SAQ training for three days per week for twelve weeks. Group II acted as control who did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical education programme. The following variables namely speed and agility were selected as criterion variables. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected dependent variables by using 50 mts run and shuttle run respectively at prior to and immediately after the training programme. The analysis of covariance was used to analyze the significant difference if any among the groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the 'F' ratio obtained by the analysis of covariance, which was considered appropriate.

Analysis of the Data:

Speed:

The analysis of covariance on speed of the pre and post test scores of SAQ training group and control group have been analyzed and presented in table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance of the Data on Speed of Pre and Post Tests Scores of SAQ Training and Control Groups

Test	SAQ Training Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained 'F' Ratio
Pre Test							
Mean	7.51	7.46	Between	0.0213	1	0.0213	1.16
S.D.	0.14	0.09	Within	0.5133	28	0.0183	
Post Test							
Mean	7.30	7.45	Between	0.1584	1	0.1584	9.28*
S.D.	0.12	0.12	Within	0.4780	28	0.0171	
Adjusted Post Test							
Mean	7.28	7.46	Between	0.2268	1	0.2268	45.92*
			Within	0.1333	27	0.0049	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence for 2 and 28 and 2 and 27 are 3.34 and 3.35 respectively).

The table 1 shows that the adjusted post-test means of SAQ training group and control group are 7.28 and 7.46 respectively on speed. The obtained "F" ratio of 45.92 for adjusted post-test means is more than the table value of 3.35 for df 1 and 27 required for significance at .05 level of confidence on speed.

The results of the study indicated that there was a significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of SAQ training group and control group on speed.

Agility:

The analysis of covariance on agility of the pre and post test scores of SAQ training group and control group have been analyzed and presented in table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance of the Data on Agility of Pre and Post Tests Scores of SAQ Training and Control Groups

Test	SAQ Training Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained 'F' Ratio
Pre Test							
Mean	8.36	8.38	Between	0.003	1	0.003	0.22
S.D.	0.11	0.09	Within	0.380	28	0.014	
Post Test							
Mean	8.17	8.34	Between	0.208	1	0.208	11.36*
S.D.	0.11	0.11	Within	0.514	28	0.018	
Adjusted Post Test							
Mean	8.18	8.33	Between	0.173	1	0.173	39.31*
			Within	0.119	27	0.004	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence for 2 and 28 and 2 and 27 are 3.34 and 3.35 respectively).

The table 2 shows that the adjusted post-test means of SAQ training group and control group are 8.18 and 8.33 respectively on agility. The obtained "F" ratio of 39.31 for adjusted post-test means is more than the table value of 3.35 for df 1 and 27 required for significance at .05 level of confidence on agility.

The results of the study indicated that there was a significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of SAQ training group and control group on agility.

Conclusions:

- There was a significant difference between SAQ training group and control group on speed and agility.
- And also it was found that there was a significant improvement on selected criterion variables such as speed and agility due to SAQ training.

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